

Hypertext fiction as stimulus – A new experimental approach to studying identification and recent findings

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An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Identification has remained an area of limited empirical investigation across disciplines, despite widespread interest in identities, roles and self–representation. This paper reviews the main strands of earlier work, noting that research has often focused on either lived identities or group membership, with comparatively little attention to how people identify with fictional characters. Building on this gap, the paper introduces a recent experimental approach that employs hypertext fiction story-games as controlled stimulus material. This method makes it possible to measure participants' self-reported identification with a protagonist under different conditions, while keeping the research environment naturalistic through online delivery. Key design considerations are discussed, including the use of original characters, controlled agency, and ecological validity. The paper then provides an integrated summary of findings from a series of studies that have used this method, demonstrating that identification varies as a function of narrative agency, character attributes, morality, winning or losing, and player characteristics such as severe depression or anxiety. Practical implications for game design and creative practice are outlined, together with the relevance of these findings to understanding identity processes. The paper concludes by proposing directions for future research to further develop this experimental methodology and deepen the theoretical understanding of identification with fictional characters

Keywords: agency; game; hypertext; identification; identity

The study of identity can be traced back to the origins of modern psychology. James (1890) described “multiple selves”, meaning that a person contains several identities or selves. Building on this foundation, Stryker (1980) defines identity as an “internalised positional designation” for each of the roles a person fulfils in society and the internalisation of those roles. Burke and Stets (2009) further develop this line of thought by defining identity as a “set of meanings that define who one is”, with each identity falling into one of three categories: a social role, group membership, or a claimed personal characteristic. They describe how multiple agents, or identities, exist within a single person, such as a job role agent and a parent agent. These agents transact with each other within the individual, for example through the transfer of skills, and between individuals, with much social interaction occurring between specific agents, such as a worker agent and a customer agent, rather than between whole persons.

According to Burke and Stets (2009), identity theory seeks to explain the specific meanings that individuals hold for the multiple identities they claim, how these identities relate to one another for any one person, how identities influence behaviour, thoughts and emotions, and how they link individuals to wider social structures. From this perspective, identity research primarily focuses on lived identities situated within social contexts.

Experimentally studying identities is challenging due to substantial individual variation and the difficulty of reliably assessing identity-related constructs. This may be one reason why identity theory has often been more closely associated with sociology than with psychology. However, there is an established experimental tradition within psychology that focuses on identities grounded in group membership, namely social identity theory.

Social identity theory

Within social identity theory, the classic experimental paradigm is the minimal group experiment developed by Tajfel (1970). In these studies, participants are assigned to groups and asked to allocate points to other participants. Consistently, they show favouritism, or in group bias, towards members of their own group, even when they know that group assignments are random. This work suggests that people define themselves, in part, through group membership and that they favour in group members as a cognitive strategy for making sense of the social world and as a means of self reference.

Tajfel (1970) argued that people do not create their own social categories but instead adopt those available within their culture. Such categorisation can constrain thinking and contribute to an inaccurate view of the world, with the motivation to preserve self-esteem leading to systematic biases in judgement. At the same time, categorisation can also function as an efficient cognitive mechanism that reduces cognitive load and is often effective, even if it does not always produce a fully accurate model of reality (Keil, 2003).

The minimal group paradigm and the broader social identity theory framework have been critiqued on methodological and conceptual grounds (e.g. Mummendey & Schreiber, 1984, as cited in Hayes, 2000). Nevertheless, this body of work demonstrates that experimental methods can be applied to the study of identification and that new identities can be adopted spontaneously in an experimental context. At the same time, the social identity theory paradigm largely restricts its focus to group membership identities, whereas Burke and Stets (2009) argue that identities can also be based on social roles and personal characteristics.

Identification

If identity is understood as a set of meanings that define who one is, then closely related to this is identification with another. This differs in that an individual has an identity, for example based on a role, group or characteristic in which one is or is a part, whereas one identifies with something or someone that one is not. It is not clear whether this logical distinction maps onto distinct mental processes; it may be that, from the perspective of the individual, both identity and identification operate as sets of meanings in which one can invest.

There has been some limited prior research into different forms of identification. Holt (1950) discusses identification with a group, which relates to what is now referred to as in group identity within social identity theory. Freud (2010, original work published 1923) discusses identification with a real person or object, but does not explicitly consider identification with fictional characters. The distinction between identification with real persons and fictional characters may not be as clear as it appears. For instance, there may be little functional difference between identifying with the projected image of a celebrity and identifying with a fictional character, as the objective existence of the person behind the image may play a limited role in the psychological process. A similar comparison can be drawn between religious figures, who are believed by adherents to exist, and fictional characters.

Identification has also been explored within the humanities. Oatley (1994) notes that identification is a central concern in both film studies and literary studies. Igartua (2010) reports that strong identification with film characters is associated with greater enjoyment, increased cognitive elaboration, heightened dramatic impact and shifts in attitudes. McCloud (1993) argues that in comics, simple and iconic characters can enhance identification. These examples illustrate potential applications of a more precise understanding of identification, even where the claims have not been extensively tested in controlled empirical studies (Cohen, 2001).

Within game studies, Klimmt et al. (2009) define identification with a character as occurring when players perceive some of the character's attributes as part of themselves and suggest that this can alter self-perception in everyday life. Follow up empirical work by Blake et al. (2012) appears to support this claim, although design limitations mean that alternative explanations cannot be ruled out. Qualitative work by Shaw (2011) indicates that greater player control over a character's actions can strengthen the sense of identification. Research in game studies has also examined identification with avatars, defined as digital entities controlled by the player, including work by Bessiere et al. (2007), Ducheneaut et al. (2009), Jorgensen (2009), Kafai et al. (2007), Kromand (2007), Kujanpää et al. (2007), Martin (2005) and Shaw (2011). Collectively, these studies suggest that interactive media provide a rich context for investigating identification with fictional characters and digital representations.

DISCUSSION

There has been limited research into identification with fictional characters across a number of disciplines, and previous work has often lacked robust empirical investigation. This gap spans both scientific and humanities traditions, despite clear potential applications for the development of artistic and creative work. The experimental tradition associated with social identity theory demonstrates that the study of identification can be operationalised, at least within the narrow scope of group identity. The present approach extends this logic to the study of identification with fictional characters through a novel experimental framework.

Role-playing in games as an identity research method

The classic social identity theory paradigm already contains game like features. Tajfel's minimal group experiments, for instance, allocate group membership and monitor behavioural outcomes in contexts resembling simplified game structures (Tajfel, 1970). A broader comparison between experimental psychology and game formats has been discussed elsewhere (Hook, 2012). However, beyond these minimal paradigms, there exist other categories of games that are particularly conducive to the study of identity. Role-playing games appear in numerous formats, including pen and paper, computer games and live action systems. For the purposes of this paper, role playing refers to the activity of enacting a character role. As Salen Tekinbas and Zimmerman (2003) observe, the concept of an RPG can be problematic because some games marketed as RPGs can be played without any role enactment, while role playing may occur in games that are not marketed as RPGs.

The term role also appears in identity studies. McCall and Simmons (1978) use the term role identities to describe the character and role that an individual devises for themselves when occupying a particular social position. They describe a hierarchy of the self in which some identities are more

central than others. The etymology of the term role, derived from the roll of paper that provides an actor with their lines, connects directly to the act of performing a character.

Minimal ludic roleplay experiment design

The experimental approach developed in this research programme uses single player computer based role playing tasks as experimental stimulus. The use of single player formats avoids the methodological complications associated with multiplayer interaction, such as controlling for the influence of other players. Practical barriers associated with creating graphical games for experimental purposes are avoided by using hypertext fiction story games, which are essentially narrative environments in which players select choices through hyperlinks. Avoiding graphical presentation increases standardisation across conditions, devices and participants, and reduces potential confounds, such as the attractiveness of a protagonist. This approach draws on discussions of digital games as experimental stimuli in the wider literature (Järvelä et al., 2012) and aligns conceptually with the logic of Tajfel's minimal group experiments.

In hypertext fiction, the participant reads a passage of text and then selects among options through hyperlinks to determine what happens next (Aarseth, 1997). These links may be presented as page numbers in physical form or as clickable digital prompts. Hypertext fiction is often written in the second person, addressing the protagonist as "you". Aarseth (1997) argues that the reader of interactive fiction should be understood as a player within a game world rather than a passive observer. Commercial examples of hypertext story games include "Depression Quest" (Quinn, 2013) and the "Fighting Fantasy" series beginning with "The Warlock of Firetop Mountain" (Jackson & Livingstone, 1982). A broader discussion of hypertext and interactive fiction is provided by Montfort (2005).

Stimulus design

Experiments adopting this method tend to follow certain common design principles. To eliminate prior familiarity with the material, an original hypertext fiction is written specifically for research use, with original characters introduced to avoid pre-existing opinions. Although the narrative setting can be situated within a popular genre to increase participation, the content should avoid challenging material unless required ethically. The stimulus is delivered via a web browser and played on the participant's own device, which enhances ecological validity because it resembles natural digital reading and gaming environments.

At the end of the hypertext narrative, participants are directed to an online form where they provide data and give consent. Participants are free to explore the narrative without submitting data, and additional demographic information can be collected for exploratory analysis. Participants may also request withdrawal of their data, facilitated by a contact email address.

Identification with the protagonist is captured using self-report Likert type items, phrased in two different ways to reduce wording effects, with responses averaged to create the dependent measure. Independent variables comprise group assignment or personal characteristics. Where sample size allows, two independent hypotheses can be tested within the same experimental run, enabling the examination of potential interaction effects.

Experimental design

The design is typically a between participants format. The computer assigns each participant to a condition and presents a slightly different version of the hypertext narrative. Group differences can be assessed using standard statistical approaches such as t tests or ANOVA. Some experiments ask participants to complete two hypertext stories, answering identification questions after each. While this introduces an element of replication, it remains methodologically equivalent to a between participants design, as the stimulus materials differ. Within participant comparisons are less robust but can be used as supplementary analysis when appropriate.

Sampling issues and limitations

Because participation occurs online, samples are limited to individuals with internet access, proficiency in the language used, and interest in participating in a narrative based experiment. However, the online format also increases sample size and geographical diversity, which would be prohibitively difficult to achieve using laboratory based methods. Evidence from previous studies suggests that samples are diverse in terms of age and education level (Hook, 2019). A limitation of the approach is that identification is self-reported. While alternatives are difficult to envision in this context, the use of a between participants design ensures that participants are unaware of alternative conditions and therefore unlikely to infer the hypothesis.

What factors influence self-reported identification?

This methodology has now been applied in several published studies (Hook, 2019, 2022a, 2022b, 2023; Hook & Morys-Carter, 2020). Taken together, these studies allow evidence based statements about factors that influence identification.

One set of findings concerns features of the stimulus. Participants identify more strongly with characters when they are given greater agency over the protagonist's actions (Hook, 2022b). This suggests that interactive media may be more effective at fostering identification than linear media (Relajo, 2018), which is consistent with interview based findings in game studies (Shaw, 2011). Identification is also stronger when the character loses rather than wins (Hook, 2023). This result was obtained regardless of the choices made by participants, implying that narrative outcome alone influenced identification. Possible explanations include disappointment with one's own life circumstances, leading to identification with a fellow "loser", or that losing is narratively more compelling. No interaction between loss and morality was detected, although a "good" character who loses resembles the form of tragic narrative.

A second set of findings relates to characteristics of the protagonist. Participants identify more strongly with richly defined characters than with shallowly defined ones (Hook, 2022a). Simply increasing the number of role identities presented on an introductory screen produced a highly significant increase in identification. This outcome contradicts assumptions in the computer game industry that blank slate protagonists facilitate projection, and runs counter to McCloud's (1993) argument that simplified characters enhance identification. Gender also plays a role. Women identify more strongly with a female character than a male character, whereas men identify equally regardless of the character's gender (Hook, 2019). The present work did not determine why this occurs, but possible explanations include different salience of gender as an identity category for men and women or evolved patterns of same sex affiliation. Additional analyses indicate that participants of any gender identify equally with a character of undefined gender, although those who preferred not to disclose their gender reported much lower levels of identification (Hook, 2022b). Religious belief does not appear to influence identification. No evidence of own religion bias was observed when comparing Christian and non-religious protagonists among Christian and atheist participants (Hook and Morys-Carter, 2020). One possibility is that participants self-reported a religion without strong identification, although this cannot be confirmed. A similar pattern emerges with morality. Good characters elicit stronger identification than evil characters in objective morality settings (Hook, 2023). This effect was consistent across different studies and suggests that moral valence influences identification, although generalisation to subjective morality settings requires further research.

A further set of findings concerns characteristics of the player. Severe depression reduces identification with fictional characters, whereas mild, moderate or moderately severe depression does not (Hook, 2022b). This pattern was only observed in the high agency condition, suggesting that low baseline identification may mask further declines. Severe anxiety shows a comparable pattern: only severe anxiety is associated with reduced identification, and only in the high agency condition (Hook, 2022b). These findings indicate that severe affective disturbance attenuates identification, representing previously unrecognised features of depression and anxiety.

Future directions

Future research can pursue several avenues. Replication of existing findings and systematic examination of interaction effects are essential. Other hypotheses that follow naturally from this method include whether adding graphics strengthens identification, whether visual media generate stronger identification than textual media, whether hypertext stories produce stronger identification than linear stories, whether identification increases only up to a certain point, and whether shared identities between a player and a character enhance identification. Anecdotally, this method has also been adopted at undergraduate level to teach experimental design and statistics.

These lines of inquiry can help clarify the mechanisms through which identification operates and determine the extent to which findings based on hypertext fiction generalise to other formats. Establishing such parameters is important for refining theoretical models of identification, for informing the design of interactive narrative media, and for evaluating whether the approach has wider value in educational and clinical contexts.

Towards a theoretical model

Some experiments have tested multiple hypotheses simultaneously, permitting scrutiny of interaction effects, although more work is required to build a comprehensive model. An emerging possibility is that bias towards shared identity may apply primarily to group based identities rather than personal characteristic identities. In addition, there may be diminishing returns when multiple factors overlap, as observed in the low agency condition in Hook (2022b).

Practical application to artistic creation

These findings have implications for creative disciplines. If the objective is to build strong identification with a fictional character, the evidence suggests that characters should be richly defined with multiple role identities, particularly for female or mixed audiences, for whom gender of the character is more consequential. Interactive formats that provide meaningful choices appear to increase identification. Morally positive characters generate stronger identification in objective morality settings, and characters who lose may also generate more engagement, resembling tragic narrative structures. Although these conclusions are based on hypertext fiction story games, they may be provisionally applied to artistic practice until further research is conducted. The results also suggest potential clinical applications, for example in developing identification based assessments of severe depression or anxiety without the need for distressing questioning.

CONCLUSION

This paper has reviewed the study of identity and identification across several disciplines, showing that empirical work has largely focused on group based identities, with far less attention given to how people identify with fictional characters. A new experimental method was set out to address this gap, drawing on single player hypertext fiction story games as controlled stimulus material. This approach enables identification to be measured while maintaining ecological validity, and allows specific variables to be manipulated within a consistent narrative environment. The studies conducted using this method demonstrate that identification is shaped by features of the narrative stimulus, by characteristics of the fictional character, and by attributes of the player. These findings highlight that identification is not a single process but a set of related mechanisms that respond to agency, morality, narrative outcome, character richness and the psychological state of the participant.

The accumulated evidence also indicates practical implications for creative practice. Narrative design choices can strengthen or weaken identification, suggesting that this method has relevance not only to experimental psychology but also to artistic production in interactive media. In addition, the results raise possible applications within mental health research, particularly in relation to depression and anxiety, although further work is required before clinical use can be considered.

Future studies can build on this foundation by examining interaction effects between variables, by comparing hypertext stimuli with other media formats, and by exploring whether similar patterns emerge when identity is constructed through subjective rather than objective morality. As the research programme develops, it may be possible to formulate a more comprehensive theoretical model that integrates the different factors observed so far. The work presented here demonstrates that identification with fictional characters can be studied systematically, opening a route for empirical inquiry where previously there has been limited experimental knowledge.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Tampere University

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